

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 1.2 Engagement programme

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This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 1.2 Engagement programme.

Ensuring that the results from the project will reach policymakers and other stakeholders.

1.1 Background – importance of engagement

The project has created a strong network between the CCS and CCU stakeholders across Europe, to ensure that the community operates effectively and efficiently.

Active engagement with the industry, EU institutions, national governments, regional governments, the research community, and civil society is crucial and **set up as a continuous process throughout the project.**

This continuous process also includes engagement with many other bodies where CCUS is relevant, such as expert groups set up by the EU institutions – the CCUS Forum initiative and working groups, the Innovation Fund and CDR Expert Groups, etc. – and other international initiatives, such as Mission Innovation and the Clean Energy Ministerial CCUS initiative.

A key activity of the work programme is to promote greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCS and CCU activities across Europe. By proactively engaging the CCS and CCU community and building on the synergies, the project drives action on CCS and CCU vis-à-vis EU institutions and national governments and supports greater understanding of the benefits of the technologies. Shared understanding and agreement on the respective roles and contributions that the industry, the research community, civil society, national governments and the European Union each need to play to deliver CCUS. Reaching this agreement is essential in order to reach [the ambitious CCUS targets contained within the SET Plan CCUS Implementation Plan](#).

2 ENGAGEMENT

2.1 Basis for efficient engagement

The project is a Coordination and Support Action for ZEP and the IWG9. The basis for successful engagement is the membership and stakeholders that are included in the two platforms themselves:

- ZEP has a very broad membership, reaching from Oil & gas and industry companies, utilities and equipment suppliers, to researchers, trade unions and environmental NGOs. In addition, ZEP has a dedicated network – the Government Group – that gathers representatives of national governments and permanent representations in Brussels to discuss and exchange on CCUS-related developments. The group consists of 23 European Governments: Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland, United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Belgium, France, Spain, Germany, Italy, Greece, Poland, Hungary, Switzerland, Austria, Iceland, Czechia, Turkey, Ireland, Romania, Croatia, Portugal.
- The SET-Plan Implementation Plan Working Group 9 on CCUS (IWG9), also has a broad membership that includes national governments and authorities – Czechia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, The Netherlands, Turkey, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom – as well as industrial and research stakeholders.

2.2 Active engagement

ZEP and the IWG9 have a combined work programme and combined governance structure, in order to increase efficiency, impact and value added for the stakeholders.

Given the strong momentum for CCS and CCU in Europe, the many projects that are to become operational within the next 5-7 years and given the very active work programme and ZEP's role as advisor to the EU on the deployment of CCS and CCU, the project engages with policymakers and other stakeholders on a daily basis.

- The combined **one day in-person ZEP Advisory Council (AC) and IWG9 Plenary meetings** are organised every quarter to establish the strategic direction for the two platforms, take decisions on the work programme and develop advice on the steps required to advance CCS and CCU. A wide range of speakers participates from relevant DGs of the European Commission, from the European Parliament, European governments, specific CCS and CCU projects as well as the CCUS community. Some 150 attendees are participating to these meetings. This aligned and coordinated approach encourages engagement between all these policymakers and stakeholders participating.
- **The Networks – Technology, Policy & Economics, and Projects** – each meet at least three times per year and encourages engagement between participants, made up of a broad and inclusive group of stakeholders, including representatives from companies and organisations that are represented in ZEP and IWG9, as well as a wide range of other stakeholders that are supporting the work.
- The governance structure includes **a wide range of working groups**, that are focus on delivering facts and recommendations in the form of reports, input papers, consultation responses, etc. in

areas such Policy and Funding, Carbon removals, CO₂ transport by ship, CCS and CCU supply chain analysis, Communication, etc.

- **The ZEP Government Group** guarantees efficient cooperation and information exchange with Member State representatives. The work of the **ZEP External Relations Group and the Communications group**, as well as the website, newsletter and other channels, ensure that the stakeholders and wider community are kept fully informed.

The meetings of ZEP and the IWG9 are open and inclusive, engaging a wide range of stakeholders the opportunity to engage and cooperate.

2.3 Further engagement, promoting the diversity of stakeholders and the membership

- ZEP plays a central role, **actively participating and leading and supporting several workstreams, in [the EC CCUS Forum work](#)** – preparing for the upcoming EC Communication on a CCS and CCU strategy for the EU: CO₂ infrastructure, Industrial Partnerships, Expert group on CO₂ specifications, etc. This has led to continuous contacts and engagement with the EC, National Governments and more than 200 representatives from other stakeholders.
- ZEP and the IWG9 have a **broad well attended working group on carbon dioxide removal (CDR)** and is represented at the [EC expert group on CDR](#). ZEP is actively involved in the [EC Innovation Fund expert group](#), [the International CDR Mission Innovation](#) and the [Clean Energy Ministerial initiative on CCUS](#).
- *Conference: The project organised **the full day, in-person Net Zero Within Reach conference in Brussels** in April 2023, bringing together some 200 participants – from EU and Member State policymakers and a wide range of other stakeholders engaging and discussing the role that CCS and CCU technologies can play in the achievement of net-zero targets. This very timely event provided a great avenue for industry, thought leaders, policymakers, researchers, and civil society to come together and share their insights on the future of these technologies in Europe, opportunities, and challenges. (Further information under 3 below).*
- *ZEP is also **organising well attended webinars**, on areas such as “[Learning from experience in geological CO₂ storage](#)”, “[Building a European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure](#)”, and “the EC proposal for a Union certification framework for carbon removals”. These webinars feature active CCS projects, experts, and EU and National Government policymakers. (Further information under 3 below).*
- ***ZEP is hosting a policy session on the skills and training needed for CCS and the role of CCS in the energy transition at the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW)** on 22 June this year, featuring experts and speakers from projects and DG ENER and the German ministry of climate action will intervene during the policy session. The EUSEW represents an excellent opportunity to engage with key EU and national officials. (Further information under 3 below).*
- **ZEP engages with EU and National Government policymakers on a day-to-day basis** regarding policy/legislation, funding, and business model issues.

- Project representatives – ZEP and the IWG9 – are **actively participating in external events giving presentations and exchanging views in panel discussions** and have over the past year presented at some 20 external events across Europe.
- ZEP also **regularly attends meetings and calls to exchange information and views on policy and funding developments with other stakeholders**, such as the MHI, Eurogas, IOGP, BP, Fluxys, Shell, Equinor, Port of Rotterdam, the Global CCS Institute, research institutions and universities, active CCS and CCU projects, and NGOs such as the European Climate Foundation, E3G, Clean Air Task Force, and Bellona. These calls allow for informal exchange on CCS and CCU related policy and funding developments and for a coordination of activities between the different stakeholders,
- ZEP and the IWG9 also **support stakeholders that are interested in joining the work of the platforms**, the Networks and the temporary working groups, therefore contributing to the ongoing workstreams by bringing their expertise.

3 THE NET ZERO WITHIN REACH CONFERENCE IN BRUSSELS

On 26 April 2023, ZEP hosted the [Net Zero Within Reach](#) conference in Brussels, supported by CCSA.

The conference brought together some 200 participants for a full day dedicated to CCS and CCU. The theme of the conference – *Net Zero Within Reach* – set the scene for the discussions, highlighting the role that CCS and CCU technologies can play in the achievement of net-zero targets – [conference programme](#).

Taking place at a crucial time for the development of CCS and CCU technologies in Europe, the event provided a great avenue for industry, thought leaders, policymakers, researchers, and civil society to come together and share their insights on the future of these technologies in Europe, opportunities, and challenges.

The conference began with a keynote session with Ruud Kempener, member of Commissioner Kadri Simson’s cabinet, who gave an overview of the European Commission’s work on CCS and CCU and highlighted the upcoming strategy, expected at the end of the year.

ZEP's Chair, Eve Tamme, emphasised the importance of collaboration and knowledge-sharing in driving the sector forward. "As the CCS and CCU community, let's be proud and celebrate recent achievements, and stay laser-focused on our primary role: reducing and removing CO₂ emissions. Net-Zero is within reach, but it will not be easy. Industry, researchers, civil society – all perspectives will be required to make it a reality." she said.

Jonathan Briggs, CCSA's Chair, highlighted the potential of CCS and CCU to play a significant role in the United Kingdom's green transition. "CCUS is essential, not an option in the green transition, and the UK has the potential to become a global CCUS leader. There is a clear alignment in terms of the industrial clusters and areas of the UK where investment and jobs are needed." he said.

In the six panel sessions that followed, panellists and delegates engaged in discussions around:

- the EU strategy for delivering CCS and CCU,
- Investing in CCS and CCU – building Europe's green competitiveness,
- Ensuring sufficient storage – creating a Europe-wide market for CO₂ storage,
- Predictability – developing a European CO₂ transport infrastructure,
- Removing CO₂ and creating carbon markets, and
- Social acceptance and public perception.

The conference also provided a great opportunity to showcase some of Europe's key projects:

- [ANRAV](#),
- [Antwerp@C](#),
- [Aramis](#),
- [CO2Next](#),
- [the East Coast Cluster](#),
- EU2NSEA,
- [Porthos CCS](#), and
- [VikingCCS](#).

The *Net Zero Within Reach* conference highlighted the essential role of CCS and CCU technologies, including the growing carbon removal sector, in achieving net-zero targets. Enabling policies and collaboration were emphasised – the upcoming EU Strategy was seen as crucial in providing a clear and ambitious direction of travel for the sector, supported by knowledge-sharing and the identification of good practices across EU Member States. A whole-value chain approach, supported by CO₂ standardisation, as well as people and skills were highlighted as key assets to support CCUS development and deployment at-scale.

The *Net Zero Within Reach* conference was a resounding success and is intended to become an annual event, providing a valuable platform to share knowledge and showcase CCS and CCU developments in Europe.

4 UPCOMING ENGAGEMENT

Active engagement with policymakers and other stakeholders is **set up as a continuous process throughout the project.**

The upcoming engagement programmes includes organising a policy session and networking at the [EU Sustainable Energy Week](#). This policy session – [Climate neutral Europe: safeguarding jobs and industrial competitiveness](#) – will be organised on 22 June 2023, engaging EU and National Government policymakers, civil society and active CCS projects. The session will highlight the following:

The transition to climate neutrality will require a significant transformation of energy- and carbon-intensive industries, such as cement, lime, steel, and chemicals, which form the backbone of the European economy. CCS offers these sectors the most cost-effective route to decarbonisation, while preserving jobs and maintaining industrial

activity. A precondition for the development and deployment of CCS at scale is the availability of a workforce with a particular set of skills. This session will bring together experts from various organisations to discuss the potential of CCS in enabling a just transition to net-zero, and the skills necessary for its widespread deployment.

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The upcoming engagement programmes also includes engagement with EU and national Government policymakers and organising a closed roundtable seminar – **The Net-Zero Industry Act – ZEP knowledge-sharing seminar** – for MEP assistants, government representatives, energy/climate attachés, and Council staff on 13 June. The seminar is linked to the Net-Zero Industry Act regulation process among the EU institutions and aims to highlight the CCS narrative, the technologies' role and importance for the industrial decarbonisation, and its necessity for European industrial activity and jobs.

For the rest of the project period a dedicated engagement strategy with EU and National Government policymakers on policy/legislation, funding, and business model issues was initiated and will be further developed. The strategy identifies audience groups for future engagement activities:

1. Members and stakeholders
 - a. ZEP members: AC members and whomever are involved in ZEP groups and activities.
 - b. Stakeholders in the CCS/CCU/CDR/R&I communities
 - c. Other professional/academic stakeholders
2. Prospective ZEP members
3. European policymakers and decision makers
4. European (both EU and non-EU) national and regional governments/authorities
5. Media: Brussels/EU media, Energy/Climate/CCS/etc. media, general media
6. Finance institutions: insurers
7. Industries/Trade Associations

8. Civil Society (trade union, NGOs, think tanks, philanthropy) and Academia/Research
9. International organisations (IRENA, Mission Innovation, IEA, Clean Energy Ministerial...)
10. Wider public

The engagement strategy includes goals linked to deployment and deployment of CCS and CCU:

- On awareness and recognition: CCS and CCU to be broadly understood as key technologies for Europe's possibility to cost-efficiently reach climate neutrality by 2050.
- On urgency: To demonstrate the extreme importance to deploy CCS technologies at scale now, in order for the EU/Europe to reach these goals.
- On an enabling framework: To clarify what needs to be done (and to make it happen), and by whom, on policy/regulation, funding and business models, in order to ensure development and deployment of CCS and CCU, in order for the EU/Europe to reach its climate targets by 2030, 2040, and 2050.
- On a Europe-wide infrastructure: To accelerate the deployment of European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure – to enable clean and competitive energy and industrial sectors, early large-scale volumes of clean hydrogen and carbon dioxide removals.

The engagement strategy should also include goals linked to the strengthening of ZEP:

- ZEP to be the go-to advisory organisation to liaise with European policymakers at EU and National levels.
- To be the natural hub for technical discussions among stakeholders on CCS and CCU technologies/R&I in Europe.
- To increase the recognition of the ZEP brand among stakeholders across Europe, in order to increase ZEP membership with a focus on European industry/emitters.
- Short-term: To increase the recognition of ZEP's activities linked to the new Projects Network. ZEP stakeholders to feel included and involved and that their views are taken into account in the ZEP work.

A stakeholder mapping will be developed to differentiate stakeholders on their position and commitment towards CCS and CCU.

Engagement activities for the rest of the project include, among others:

- The EU Industry Days 2023 on 4-6 October in Málaga, Spain, and the 2024 edition
- The second edition of the CCUS Forum on 27-28 November 2023 in Aalborg, Denmark, and the 2024 edition
- The ZEP conference on 24 April 2024
- The EU Industry Days 2024
- The ZEP Government Group meetings in 2023 and 2024
- The ZEP External Relations Group meetings in 2023 and 2024
- The ZEP Network Technology meetings in 2023 and 2024

The ZEP Network Policy & Economics meetings in 2023 and 2024

- The 2024 European Parliament election, before which ZEP will actively engage with candidate MEPs, political advisors, and party representatives to highlight the importance of CCS and CCU as net-zero technologies.

Project representatives – ZEP and the IWG9 – will also actively participate in additional external events that are proposed to the representatives (e.g. annual conferences, industry workshops...) giving presentations and exchanging views in panel discussions.